

Report on Major Workshops and Boards

Water-ForCE

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List of Acronyms

AGRI (DG)	DG for Agriculture and Rural Development
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
CEH	Center for Ecology and Hydrology
CEMS	Copernicus Emergency Service
CLMS	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Service
DEFIS (DG)	DG for Defence Industry and Space
DG	Directorate General
DoA	Description of Action
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EEA	European Environment Agency
EMSA	European Maritime Safety Agency
ESA	European Space Agency
ENV (DG)	DG Environment
GA	Grant Agreement
GAs	General Assembly
GEMS	Global Environment Monitoring System

JRC	Joint Research Center
MARE (DG)	DG for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
RTD (DG)	DG for Research and Innovation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
UN	United Nations
WP	Work Package
WWQA	World Water Quality Alliance

Executive Summary

This report aims to give an overview of the rationale, objectives, and outcomes of the 2 main workshops organized by the Water-ForCE Consortium and the structure of the guidance received during the meetings with the Advisory Board of Water-ForCE.

The two main workshops were planned at the beginning and at the end of the Action. The first of them with the objective of gathering the opinion, suggestions and needs of the principal stakeholders related to Copernicus Services for Water and the second one to test the solutions given by the Consortium to those needs and gaps. While in the first case the discussions were around the information and opinion given by the invited key stakeholders; the draft Roadmap for the Copernicus Water Services, produced by the consortium in reply to the needs expressed by the key stakeholders, was the base for discussion during the last Workshop.

The **Copernicus water component evolution - policy expert Workshop** of Water-ForCE (Milestone 12), as it is described in the Grant Agreement, was planned to be held in a face-to-face format in the EEA in Copenhagen in June 2021. Due to COVID-19 restrictions, this could not be done. Therefore, it was decided by the Consortium to split this single event into two complementary ones, built upon the results obtained in previous workshops with stakeholders (WP1 Workshop, Milestone1): the first fully virtual event was held during the planned dates inside of the Water Innovation Europe Conference 2021 (14-18 June) and the second one, was held in hybrid format during 20th-21st October 2021; being the in-person part in Copenhagen, as it was initially planned and reflected in the GA.

During the following 2 years, the Water-ForCE Consortium analysed the delivery of different water related services and products by the six Copernicus Services and compared them to the needs and expectations of all relevant sectors and communities. The results of these analyses were summarised in the Water-ForCE Roadmap for the Future of Copernicus for Water; and its main outcomes were discussed with the most relevant actors in September 27th – 28th in Brussels during the **Key Stakeholders Workshop of Water-ForCE**, reflected in the GA as MS13.

8.6.1 Copernicus water component evolution – policy expert

Copernicus water component evolution – policy expert

October 20th and 21st 2021 | Hybrid: Online and Phoenix Copenhagen Hotel | Free registration

We will address the current disconnects between remote sensing and in situ observation research, deliver clarity in terms of the needs and expectations of the public and private sectors of the core Copernicus Program and the wider research and business innovation opportunities.

The entrusted entities and European policy institutions are a key actor and driver of new developments, which are currently ongoing in Copernicus 2.0. To deliver a roadmap that is relevant and actionable, we would like to present our activities and results to date and learn from you where action is already being taken and where you see priorities and opportunities.

[See full programme here](#)

[See Roadmap Skeleton](#)

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1 Introduction

For the objectives stated in the GA of Water-ForCE, the first WP1 workshop (20th April; MS1) was considered a successful event in terms of participation (62 attendees from 11 countries) and outcomes. However, some stakeholder's types (identified key users) were identified as underrepresented:

- Commercial water users
- Industry sector
- Water for agriculture users/managers

These (and other) user communities were the ones targeted through participation in the Water Innovation Europe Conference 2021 (14th-18th June, 2021) through a Water-ForCE virtual booth.

However, it was decided that, in order to prepare a Roadmap that takes into account future plans of all key players in the field, a face-to-face meeting with them was still needed. Therefore, the second workshop in hybrid format was held in Copenhagen in October 2021, where we were targeting another stakeholders' typology, considered crucial to achieve the Water-ForCE objectives: namely experts from the EU Agencies and Institutions (EEA, JRC, DGs, etc), entrusted entities (ECMWF, Mercator Ocean International, EUMETSAT), Copernicus

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Academy, ESA, and international organizations. The workshop was by invitation only, so not open to the general community. This workshops' scheme was intended to complement other workshops and thus cover the whole stakeholders' spectrum. This helped us understand better to which direction the relevant organizations see Copernicus water related services developing in the coming years, in order to prepare an actionable Roadmap that takes the key stakeholders activities into account. This workshop was prepared using the two previous virtual events outcomes and key findings as the starting point.

1.1 Rationale behind the schedule

The event was organized around 3 thematic blocks (Tables 1-3) which were intended to cover all the aspects covered by the key players in the Copernicus Services who are actually delivering, needing or using water related data. The 3 thematic blocks are:

- Copernicus Technical Developments and Needs
 - EEA, JRC and ESA representatives
- Policy Developments and their Impact on Copernicus Services
 - DGs representatives (ENV, RTD, MARE, AGRI)
 - WATER4ALL Partnership
- Copernicus Services. Present and Future.
 - Copernicus Services
- International Organizations (UN)

To ensure the protection of personal data no personal opinion will be disclosed in this report.

1.2 Workshop Introduction (Water-ForCE) and General Considerations (DG DEFIS)

The event was opened by Dr. Tiit Kutser, Coordinator of Water-ForCE CSA, who introduced the project to the audience, including results up to date and an outline of the RoadMap.

This was followed by DG DEFIS general considerations about Copernicus Services and Water-ForCE Action. DG DEFIS develops and implements the Commission's policies on defence industry and space, which were previously carried out by the Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs (DG GROW). In the area of Space DG DEFIS is in charge of implementing the EU Space programme consisting of the European Earth Observation Programme (Copernicus), the European Global Navigation Satellite System (Galileo) and the European Geostationary Navigation Overlay Service (EGNOS). Inside of Its responsibilities Is to Implement the future Space Programme covering EGNOS, Galileo and Copernicus.

It was highlighted the importance of the **continuity** of the Services already being delivered; the importance of the water secur inside of the **EU Green Deal**, and the maintenance of a constant dialog regarding **WFD** and work inside of the **UN SDG** framework. Another element to be considered is that the mandate and responsibility are at National Level. The Commission just brings the needed support.

2 Block 1. Technical developments and needs

In this block the EEA and ESA explained to the Water-ForCE Consortium their current and expected developments and needs in the water domain.

	European Environment Agency	Speaker	Institution
1	Copernicus Land Service		
	User needs and CLMS perspective on water products	Hans Doufourmont	EEA
	The Copernicus Land Service Global activities. Water products	Michael Cherlet	EC JRC
2	EEA Marine and Water		
	Technical developments and needs for marine and freshwater products	Monika Peterlin Nihat Zal	EEA
3	Copernicus in situ		
	The Copernicus In Situ Component	Henrik S. Andersen	EEA
	European Space Agency		
4	ESA R&D Activities on Water for Science and Applications		
	ESA work towards SDGs on water	Marc Paganini	ESA
	ESA Science-driven Activities on Water	Espen Volden	ESA

Table 1.- Block 1 presentations.

2.1 EEA - JRC Copernicus Land Service

2.1.1 User needs and CLMS perspective on water products

Apart from the content of the presentation which includes the water related products inside of CLMS and current challenges, specifically for freshwater products, it was highlighted:

- More efficiency into the productive chain: harmonization of products
- Integration of different products
- Combination of EO with *in situ* data

2.1.2 The Copernicus Land Service Global activities. Water products.

The CLMS goes to from global to European to local scale, being the Implementation of the first one entrusted to JRC and the remaining 2 to the EEA.

Description of the global bio-geophysical products delivered. It was highlighted the need for in situ data for **Lake Water Quality Product**.

Presented the Freshwater Ecosystem Explorer.

2.2 EEA Marine and Water

2.2.1 Technical developments and needs for marine and freshwater products.

The strategic objectives of EEA were presented and the marine products (evaluation of policies, collaboration with Marine Service).

Highlighted the importance of **HR data** for Regional Assessments and identification of long-term trends.

They work with **16 marine indicators and 4 of them use EO** (Copernicus) data.

Needs of Information from the freshwater side:

- The policies need to Identify the distance to targets.
- The water data should be Integrated coming from different sources.
- Importance of data from National programs.

2.3 EEA Copernicus In situ

2.3.1 The Copernicus *in situ* component

They provide data to the Copernicus Services and to the Space Component, strictly relying on external data EEA work as a coordinator, while the Services, ESA and EUMETSAT work directly with data providers.

EEA has the role to engage (through partnerships and agreements) with data providers to Copernicus.

2.4 ESA R&D Activities on Water for Science and applications

It was offered an overview of all the ESA R&D activities related to water Including wetlands and coastal areas, most of them in support of UN SDG 6.

Looking Into the future: Joint EC-ESA Earth System Science Initiative.

3 Block 2. Policy developments and their impact in Copernicus Services.

The 2nd block was devoted to the current work of the DGs related to water and how Copernicus Services are being or can be used in the future to cover policy needs.

	Directorates General	Speaker	Institution
1	DG ENV		
	Copernicus for Water Policy	Hugo De Groof	DG ENV
2	DG RTD		
	Water R&I in Horizon Europe	Panagiotis Balabanis	DG RTD
3	DG MARE		
	Interdependence between in situ observations and satellite remote sensing.	Grigore Rischitor	DG MARE
4	DG AGRI		
	Copernicus Services and Sustainable Water Management in Agriculture	Marta Iglesias	DG AGRI
	Opportunities for the use of EO data.	Isidro Campos	DG AGRI
5	WATER4ALL PARTNERSHIP		
	Water4all Partnership	Olivier Bouc	ANR

Table 2.- Block 2 presentations.

3.1 Directorates-General

3.1.1 DG ENV. Copernicus for water policy

It was discussed how to support EU Green Deal objectives. How to include information from all basins. It was discussed a Risk Based approach and how Water-ForCE might work on Compliance of Directives.

The discussions about data shortcomings derived towards the harmonization between sources (ie. Member States) and between different temporal scales; access and quality.

3.1.2 Water research and Innovation in Horizon Europe.

The presentation was devoted to the role of HEurope in progressing towards state of the art in water research.

3.1.3 DG MARE. Interdependence between in situ observations and satellite remote sensing.

EMODnet and Its collaboration with CMEMS. Regional focus towards the **Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)**. EO In support of Blue **Economy** (eg. Aquaculture)

DG AGRI. Copernicus Services and Sustainable Water Management in Agriculture. Opportunities for the use of EO data.

They need Copernicus data mostly for water availability/use evaluation. Smart combination of Copernicus and In situ data

Different levels In EO applications: CAP Indicators, reporting (policies), decision making and early warning systems.

- Land use

- Irrigation

4 Block 3. Copernicus Services. Present and Future

Copernicus Services		
4	Copernicus Marine Service	
	CMEMS status and plans for Copernicus 2 with a focus on coastal zones.	Pierre-Yves Letraon Mercator O.
5	Copernicus Climate Change Service	
	Copernicus Climate Change Service	Carlo Buontempo ECMWF
6	Copernicus Emergency Service	
	Emergency Management Service	Vera Thiemig JRC
7	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service	
	CLMS Water related information	Hans Douformount EEA
	CLMS GLOBAL Activities.	Michael Cherlet JRC
8	Copernicus Security Service	
	EMSA EO Services	Paula Martí EMSA
9	EUMETSAT	
		Hayley Evers-King EUMETSAT

Table 3.- Block 3 presentations.

4.1 Copernicus Services

All these talks had self-explanatory presentations.

4.1.1 Copernicus Marine Service. CMEMS status and plans for Copernicus 2 with a focus on coastal zones.

Evolution on Copernicus Marine for Coastal Users/Next Steps.

4.1.2 Copernicus Climate Change Service - C3S.

The Service aims to help a broad range of water managers for water allocation, flood

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management, ecological status and industrial water use, with information on:

- Climate change in water related variables
- Hydrological seasonal forecasts

It offers:

- Ensembles of hydrological impact models (Data available in the CDS-Catalogue)
- Applications built with the CDS-Toolbox to explore the data
- Practical showcases on how to use the service
- User guidance on the data and related activities

<https://climate.copernicus.eu/operational-service-water-sector>

4.1.3 Copernicus Emergency Service. Emergency Management Service

CEMS evolution under Copernicus 2.0 Includes Establishing close links to relevant research programs at European and national level (H2020 - e.g. G3P, ECFAS, **Water-ForCE**, Horizon Europe)

4.1.4 Copernicus Land Monitoring Service.

CLMS Water Related Information

Diversity of water related products

- Can they be integrated into a smaller number?
- Can they be better harmonized?
- What are the missing elements to be included via EO / in situ?
- What is the potential for synergies with other Copernicus services?
- From status / change towards more continuous monitoring?

CLMS GLOBAL Activities.

CLMS Is developing plug-Ins for QGIS.

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Open Source on Git-Hub repo.

GBOV Service. Ground Observations. (high quality data to validate 7 core products).

4.1.5 Copernicus Security Service. EMSA EO Services

4.2 International Organizations

	International Organizations	Speaker	Institution
1	UN GEMS Water		
	Towards a global freshwater observing system supporting UN policies and frameworks	Philipp Saile	UN
2	World Water Quality Alliance		
	The World Water Quality Alliance	Nina Raasakka	UN
3	GEO		
	GEO and Water-ForCE Roadmap	Douglas Cripe	GEO

4.2.1 UN: GEMS Water and WWQA.

Very thorough presentations (see in our shared folder)

From GEMS Water vision on how the **Evolution of Copernicus services to support global freshwater observing systems** could be:

Provision of in situ water monitoring data for cal/val of remote sensing products

- Definition of reference sites, targeted data collection
- Clarification of data usage

Improving existing Copernicus service products relevant for freshwater monitoring

- Higher spatial and temporal resolution for temperature, Chl-a, Turbidity products to allow

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for monitoring of riverine systems

- Provision of waterbody & basin level aggregates/statistics

Integrating freshwater and other service's products

- Water quantity
- Water quality
- Hydromorphological & basin characteristics

4.2.2 GEO. GEO and Water-ForCE Roadmap

GEO is a **facilitator of policy-level dialogue** on the importance and coordination of Earth observation systems.

Importance of Integrating observations from different sources (In situ, EO...)

GEOglows Is Important for Water-ForCE as a potential Service for Copernicus

GEO Knowledge Hub: digital repository for EO applications

Annex 1

Agenda

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WORKSHOP PROGRAMME: 20th October 2021, 13:00 – 19:00 CEST

Copernicus water component evolution – policy expert

Hybrid: Online and Phoenix Copenhagen Hotel

12:00	13:00	Lunch at the Phoenix Hotel
13:00	13:05	Welcome and logistics: Tiit Kutser
13:05	13:35	Water-ForCE intro, results to date and outline of the Roadmap: Tiit Kutser
13:35	13:40	DG DEFIS General Considerations: Michel Massart
Block 1: Presentations on technical developments and needs		
13:40	14:05	EEA (Copernicus, Water, Marine, in situ) EEA-JRC Copernicus Land Service: Hans Dufourmont & Michael Cherlet
14:05	14:20	EEA Marine & Water: Stéphane Isoard
14:20	14:35	EEA Copernicus in situ: Henrik Andersen
14:35	14:50	ESA Future plans: Marc Paganini
14:50	15:05	New Sensors: Espen Volden
15:05	15:30	Discussion (Moderated discussion with the outline of the Roadmap as a basis)
15:30	16:00	Coffee break (Hybrid with a virtual moderated option)
Block 2: Presentations of policy developments and their impact on Copernicus Services		
16:00	16:15	EU Directorates General DG ENV: Hugo de Groof
16:15	16:30	DG RTD: Panagiotis Balabanis
16:30	16:45	DG MARE: Grigore Rischitor
16:45	17:00	DG AGRI: Marta Iglesias
17:00	17:15	WATER4ALL: Olivier Bouc
17:15	18:30	Discussion (Moderated discussion with the outline of the Roadmap as a basis)
18:30	19:00	Discussion and wrap up of day 1: Tiit Kutser

Join meeting: <https://us06web.zoom.us/j/87957582405?pwd=aHZUR3ZaNkw3NWU5Yi8vMXNlczR2UT09>

Meeting ID: 879 5758 2405

Passcode: 339692

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WORKSHOP PROGRAMME: 21st October 2021, 09:00 – 13:00 CEST

Copernicus water component evolution – policy expert

Hybrid: Online and Phoenix Copenhagen Hotel

Block 3: Presentations about Copernicus Services present and future		
09:00	09:10	Introduction to the day: Tiit Kutser
		International Organizations
09:10	09:25	UN GEMS Water: Philipp Saile
09:25	09:40	World Water Quality Alliance (WWQA): Nina Raasakka
09:40	09:55	GEO: Douglas Cripe
		Copernicus Services
09:55	10:10	EUMETSAT: Hayley Evers-King
10:10	10:25	Copernicus Marine Service: Pierre-Yves LeTraon
10:25	10:40	Copernicus Climate Change Service: Carlo Buontempo
10:40	10:55	Copernicus Emergency Service: Vera Thiemig
10:55	11:10	Copernicus Land Service: Hans Dufourmont & Michael Cherlet
11:10	11:25	Copernicus Security Service: Paula Martí
11:25	11:50	Coffee break (Hybrid with a virtual moderated option)
11:50	13:00	Discussion and summary
13:00	14:00	Lunch at the Phoenix Hotel

Join meeting: <https://us06web.zoom.us/j/83579684059?pwd=ZHhyUmRTbXBkUnJlcHBFTUhhGNjRtdz09>

Meeting ID: 835 7968 4059

Passcode: 262704

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8.6.2. Key Stakeholders workshop. 27th – 28th September, 2023. Brussels.

During the last 3 years, the Water-ForCE Consortium analysed the delivery of different water related services and products by the six Copernicus Services and compared them to the needs and expectations of all relevant sectors and communities. The results of these analyses were summarised in the Water-ForCE Roadmap for the Future of Copernicus for Water.

The main outcomes of the Roadmap were discussed with the most relevant actors during the Workshop, analysed and further implemented towards the last version of the Roadmap.

The discussions during the workshop were organised around the following topics:

- Current state of play of the Copernicus Programme for water. Bottlenecks and opportunities.
- Priority Actions for Copernicus for Water
- Scenarios for Copernicus for Water

All the registered participants got the latest version of the Roadmap together with the workshop agenda two weeks before the workshop in order to allow fruitful discussions during the workshop.

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1 Summary of participants

The identity of the participants in the workshop is protected and therefore we will not overly quantify the results. For the bottlenecks session there were 52 participants, while in the priority session we had 41 and in the scenarios' session 40. All participants were invited by the Water-ForCE team covering all the thematic working group experts, representatives of EU policy making bodies and Agencies as well as Entrusted Entities. There was a strong majority of individuals from research institutes, primarily from national level research bodies and universities. Some of the private sector participants are also involved in research but also represent the needs of downstream economies. Participants from international governing bodies, including entrusted entities and different levels of the EU structure, were a minority but represented key decision makers for the Copernicus Programme for Water.

Table 1. Summary of the participants organisation's sector. These results were anonymous and therefore we just use the general level descriptor.

Organisation's sector	Bottlenecks	Priority Ac.	Scenarios
Decisionmaking bodies (International governing bodies / entrusted entities / EC etc)	10	6	12
Private sector (EO service providers)	8	5	6
Research institute (national, university etc)	26	10	14
Other or did not respond to the question	8	20	8

2 Bottlenecks session

2.1 Prioritisation of bottlenecks

Individuals were asked to organise the bottlenecks into a priority list. The result is as shown in Figure 1 below. **Lack of dedicated water in-situ component appears as the highest rated bottleneck**, followed by Sentinels are suboptimal for inland waters. Both of these are infrastructural and data related bottlenecks which are then translated into our priority actions (PA01 and PA02). Thirdly, the lack of awareness within important user communities was selected (PA04). Fourthly, the lack of compatibility between EO and EU directives and other international monitoring initiatives (e.g. SDG's) were selected.

Figure 1. Prioritisation of the bottlenecks

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2.2 Timeline for achieving

Following the same colour scheme as the prioritisation, the bottlenecks have been organised into the timeline within which most of the participants thought this bottleneck can be solved (i.e. the maximum number of votes). For a breakdown of the votes per bottleneck, please refer to Section 3. Notably, the consensus was that all the bottlenecks can be solved before 2034. The vast majority of these bottlenecks are to be solved within the next budget cycle. There are two bottlenecks which were believed to be solvable in the current budget. These are the lack of awareness within important user communities and the limited trust in Copernicus water products. Possibly this is because these two bottlenecks are presumed to be primarily capacity building in nature and may not require substantial infrastructural changes to enact.

Table 1. Sentiment analysis of current bottlenecks. From the left-right timeframe within which they can likely be solved.

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2.3 Summary of each bottleneck

2.3.1 Bottleneck 1: Lack of dedicated water in-situ component

Overall, most of the participants agreed that the lack of a dedicated water in-situ component is a bottleneck (Figure 2A). From this majority, actions to address this bottleneck commonly included the themes of dedicated funding, coordination among in-situ providers to harmonise monitoring protocol and support for countries with different capacity levels. It was also found that the next Copernicus budget (2028 -2034) would be the appropriate cycle for these actions to take place and the bottleneck to be addressed (Figure 2B).

A

B

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international effort and country-level responsibility. The Copernicus Programme, itself, was not seen as responsible for solving this bottleneck.

Participants were finally asked what their own organisation can contribute to solving this bottleneck. Given that the governing bodies were identified as being responsible for solving this bottleneck, we make a note of analysing these responses separately. There were at least two participants from European governing bodies which identified the establishing of in-situ programmes to be within their responsibility. Other governing bodies identified the establishment of methodologies for harmonising monitoring, direct policy and propose/amend and legislation and working with member states to improve data collection for EO to be within their responsibility. Of participants from other sectors, there were also several responsibilities taken, including the implementation/ collection of in-situ data, sharing data, developing protocol for harmonisation of data collection, and increasing awareness of EO needs from in-situ data collection programmes. One suggestion from the private sector was to use policy to encourage private companies to make data openly available.

2.3.2 Bottleneck 2: Limited trust in Copernicus water products

The bottleneck ‘Limited trust in Copernicus water products’ was discussed during the session and was not well received by all members as some people deemed the term ‘trust’ as derogatory. The consortium has used these terms to include both actual trustworthiness of products and data as well as the lack of uncertainty information to calculate trust. More on this can be found in the relevant section of the Roadmap. Overall most participants had no strong agreement or disagreement on this bottleneck (i.e. agreement around 5) (Figure 4). The types of actions suggested can largely be grouped into two; firstly the improvement of validation of products and uncertainties, and secondly, the increased communication to actual end users.

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Figure 4. Results for bottleneck 2 for the questions, **A)** To what extent do you agree that this bottleneck needs solving, **B)** On what timescale do you think this bottleneck can be solved?, **C)** Who do you think should solve this bottleneck? and **C)** How can this bottleneck be solved?

When asked **who was responsible for solving this bottleneck**, the Copernicus Programme and Services were strongly cited (Figure 5). Additionally, it was also regarded that ‘everyone’ and ‘all stakeholders’ should contribute to solving this bottleneck.

Mostly, participants identified their organisations as contributing a) various quality assurance services and b) capacity building. Regarding services, some governing bodies and

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private companies suggested providing services to develop evaluation and quality services, adapting products, algorithm prototyping and also mention of the European Digital Twin of the Ocean. It was also clear that most participants saw their contribution to solving this bottleneck as a capacity building task, which were far more commonly suggested. These included building feedback mechanisms and engagement with users, training and communication.

2.3.3 Bottleneck 3: Lack of compatibility between EO and EU directives or international monitoring initiatives

The participants had overall agreement with this bottleneck but there were also some participants who did not consider this to be an issue (Figure 6). Additionally, there was one participant who strongly disagreed with the statement. Of those that scored this bottleneck below 5, there were few comments as to why. In general, the solution for this bottleneck was suggested to be communication and also updating directives. The statements with the highest number of upvotes were “Communication between the different European entities” and “Updating the implementation procedures of the directives, to include EO”. In terms of who can solve this bottleneck, and presumably who should do these suggested actions, it was very clear that the European Commission was the number 1 body participants identified. Additionally, Copernicus and EU DG’s were also identified.

In terms of identifying the contribution of their own organisations, governing bodies, although being identified by the group at large at being capable of this, did not see compatibility as an issue, while other governing bodies found their roles to be on facilitating dialogue between relevant parties and coordination. Meanwhile, a number of participants from private sector and research institutes did not identify a role for their organisation in solving this bottleneck.

participants which strongly disagree with this statement. Those that strongly disagreed with the bottleneck noted that topics should be merged and there should be one platform for all services. Interestingly, the same solutions were predominantly suggested by those who strongly agreed with this statement, including a single platform, single website which links to all services etc.

Figure 5. Results for bottleneck 4 for the questions, **A)** To what extent do you agree that this bottleneck needs solving, **B)** On what timescale do you think this bottleneck can be solved?, **C)**

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Who do you think should solve this bottleneck? and **C)** How can this bottleneck be solved?

Copernicus was identified as the main entity that can solve this bottleneck and the timeframe for achieving this was a mixture of the current and future Copernicus budgets. In addition, when asked what participants' own organisation can offer, there were some clear indications among the relevant organisations that they take responsibility for initiating a dialogue, establishing a Water entrusted entity and also even developing a Water Service. Regarding the contribution of non-decision making bodies, some participants found they could offer advice, while many did not believe they had anything to contribute.

2.3.5 c.5. Bottleneck 5: Sentinels suboptimal for inland waters

There was strong agreement with the bottleneck that Sentinels are suboptimal for inland waters. There were a minority of participants who had a neutral position towards this bottleneck. Solutions for this bottleneck included numerous references to investment in new missions and also the increased promotion of water as a critical focus in the Copernicus Programme. Notably, the solution with the highest upvotes was the supplementation of Sentinel data with other providers and various comments also alluded to the need for collaboration. There was also the suggestion to consolidate inland water users' needs for Space agencies.

Figure 6. Results for bottleneck 5 for the questions, **A)** To what extent do you agree that this bottleneck needs solving, **B)** On what timescale do you think this bottleneck can be solved?, **C)** Who do you think should solve this bottleneck? and **C)** How can this bottleneck be solved?

Space agencies and the European Space Agency (ESA) were identified as the most important body to solve this bottleneck. Notably, most non-Space entities did not identify a responsibility except sharing their needs and promoting the importance of inland water. Some research organisations identified a role of advising, R&D through projects and

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innovation. Certain Space and entrusted entities acknowledged that this was already a goal for them.

2.3.6 Bottleneck 6: Lack of funding mechanism supporting enlargement of Copernicus Services inland water portfolio

There was a large distribution between strongly disagreeing and strongly agreeing. Although funding was repeated as the solution by many participants, there was also discussion on the topic that funding may already exist but it is about reorganisation of mechanisms to deliver funds towards enlarging the Copernicus portfolio for Water. Governing bodies in attendance were also about to point the direction to where these funding opportunities and mechanisms might already be available (e.g., Horizon Cluster 4 and 5 Copernicus SME scheme). The next budget was identified as the timeframe within which this bottleneck can be overcome and there were mixed ideas of who should do this, including the EU and European Commission, Copernicus Programme and simply everyone. Many participants found that their organisations could contribute advice and lobbying. None of the participants identified their organisations as responsible for solving this bottleneck but it was noted that cooperation with the Copernicus Services is necessary in distributing funds.

Figure 7. Results for bottleneck 6 for the questions, **A)** To what extent do you agree that this bottleneck needs solving, **B)** On what timescale do you think this bottleneck can be solved?, **C)** Who do you think should solve this bottleneck? and **C)** How can this bottleneck be solved?

2.3.7 Bottleneck 7: Lack of awareness within important user communities

This bottleneck was fairly strongly agreed among the majority of participants. Even those that scored this bottleneck as ‘strongly disagree’ provided some solutions to the bottleneck. In general it was agreed that this could be solved within the current Copernicus budget and

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was found to be the responsibility of everyone. The most important actions to make this happen were identified as communication and bringing EO closer to users through a user friendly platform, training and outreach. In general, most participants found their organisations to have some contribution to increasing awareness within important user communities. These included actions involving communication of end-user needs, sharing data and advocating for water. Notably, decision making bodies were overall in strong agreement with this bottleneck although commitments on this issue were somewhat vague and often missing.

A

B

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Figure 8. Results for bottleneck 7 for the questions, **A)** To what extent do you agree that this bottleneck needs solving, **B)** On what timescale do you think this bottleneck can be solved?, **C)** Who do you think should solve this bottleneck? and **C)** How can this bottleneck be solved?

2.3.8 Bottleneck 8: Water domains are insufficiently prioritised within the Copernicus Programme

Finally, agreement with the last bottleneck, regarding the role of Water as a priority within the Copernicus Programme, was highly distributed. However, even those that scored this bottleneck as ‘strongly disagree’ provided some solutions to the bottleneck. Notably, private companies scored this bottleneck particularly low, while public research institutions scored this bottleneck much higher, on average. To address this bottleneck, the term Water Service was mentioned many times among different sectors, and also the suggestion that Water products and Services be included at a higher level of finability. In general it was agreed that this could be solved within the current and next copernicus budget, and lobbies were identified as key players in making this happen. While many participants did not feel their organisations had a role in making this happen, those that did, regardless of the sector,

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generally felt their contribution would be to demonstrate how important water is and EO applications.

Figure 9. Results for bottleneck 8 for the questions, **A)** To what extent do you agree that this bottleneck needs solving, **B)** On what timescale do you think this bottleneck can be solved?, **C)** Who do you think should solve this bottleneck? and **C)** How can this bottleneck be solved?

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3 Priority Actions Session

During this session, the Priority Actions (PA) described in the last version of the Roadmap were tested with the attendees in 2 steps. First, the PA were summarized and grouped in 4 thematic clusters that were discussed separately around the answers from the attendees to the question “*What are the necessary steps needed for these Priority Actions to be carried out?*”. In the following chapters we will describe the results obtained for every PA thematic cluster.

3.1 PA01: Enhance in situ observations for calibration and validation.

Priority Actions

PA01: Enhance In situ observations for calibration and validation

- 1.1. Establish cal/val supersites around the world representative of optical variability in water bodies, observing variables that are also observable with satellites.
- 1.2 Adapt member state monitoring schemes to increase compatibility with satellite Earth Observation
- 1.3 Coordinate and agree the collection of observation data to support enhanced and new satellite-based products
- 1.4 Build FAIR data repositories to store and share relevant in situ observation data

Figure 10. Priority actions cluster PA01.

3.1.1 Establish cal/val supersites around the world representative of optical variability in water bodies, observing variables that also observable with satellites (22 responses).

The necessary steps discussed by the attendees for this PA to be carried out can be summarized as follows:

- Collaboration and coordination activities: National and international collaboration to find suitable sites and already existing networks. Name a responsible institution.
- Technological: Clearly define variables needed. Study the optical variability of waterbodies. Develop a standardized protocol with specific methodology to allow interoperability and comparability of measurements.
- Funding.

3.1.2 Adapt Member States monitoring schemes to increase compatibility with satellite Earth Observation (18 responses):

The necessary steps discussed by the attendees for this PA to be carried out can be summarized as follows:

- Coordination and collaboration: with stakeholders and national authorities. Be aware of the “resistance to change” inside of the administrations and agencies. EO data need to be referred in EU and national directives and policies. Collaboration with national HydMet services.
- Communication, outreach, lobbying and capacity building activities: Demonstrate the value of the in situ observations for cal/val.
- Funding

3.1.3 Coordinate and agree the collection of observation data to support enhanced and new satellite-based products (14 responses):

The necessary steps discussed by the attendees for this PA to be carried out can be summarized as follows:

- Coordination and collaboration: dialogue with experts and stakeholders including EU and national agencies and international organizations (space agencies, CEOS, GEO, WMO, etc.).
- Communication, outreach and capacity building: Promote holistic approaches (in situ data, modelling & remote sensing) towards the same goal: water management. Illustrate benefits.
- Policy: Data collection based on reporting obligations (eg. WFD)
- Technological: Start with small missions at national level as demonstration and scale up.

3.1.4 Build FAIR data repositories to store and share relevant in situ observation data (15 responses):

The necessary steps discussed by the attendees for this PA to be carried out can be summarized as follows:

- Coordination: work with already existing national FAIR repositories. International collaboration to avoid duplication of efforts. Improve IPRs and licenses of use. Identify a responsible organization for Data Management.
- Technological: Appropriate automated upload of data in NRT with QC protocols. Periodic reassessment of protocols. Define metadata, protocols and formats.

3.2 PA02: A comprehensive satellite observation capability to exploit water products and services.

Priority Actions

PA02: A comprehensive satellite observation capability to exploit in Water products and services

- 2.1 Sufficient spatial and temporal resolution to resolve aquatic systems
- 2.2 Appropriate optical wavebands (up to hyperspectral) for water quality estimates in all environments
- 2.3 Appropriate radiometric resolution to resolve all features
- 2.4 Appropriate sun glint avoidance across all instruments
- 2.5 Virtual constellations to aid data integration and harmonisation

Figure 11. Priority actions cluster PA02.

3.2.1 Sufficient spatial and temporal resolution to resolve aquatic systems (16 responses):

The necessary steps discussed by the attendees for this PA to be carried out can be summarized as follows:

- Coordination: Motivate the need by showcasing the possibilities. Make connections with other communities (eg. Modelling) to overcome the EO limitations in resolution.
- Technological: Clearly define what can be done with the available technology and perform a sound analysis on what is really needed. Be specific with clear justification cost-driven to describe what would be “sufficient”. The requirements should be stated as product/application driven.

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3.2.2 Appropriate optical wavebands (up to hyperspectral) for water quality estimates in all environments (9 responses):

The necessary steps discussed by the attendees for this PA to be carried out can be summarized as follows:

- Coordination: Influence the Next Mission by highlighting water as crucial in the coming years due to Climate Change.
- Technological: Describe requirements with justification to S3NG and S2NG Mission Advisory Groups. Other requirements cited by the attendees were the need for spectral bands to resolve cyanobacteria, plastic, etc.; increasing the temporal resolution of hyperspectral sensors.

3.2.3 Appropriate radiometric resolution to resolve all features (4 responses):

This PA was replied by few people due to its technical nature. The necessary steps discussed by the attendees for this PA to be carried out can be summarized as follows:

- Coordination: Perform a meta-study summarizing existing information and add additional sensitivity studies where there are gaps.
- Technological: SAR images for water quantity and altimetry.

3.2.4 Appropriate sun glint avoidance across all instruments (4 responses):

This PA was replied by few people due to its technical nature. The necessary steps discussed by the experts present for this PA to be carried out can be summarized as follows:

- Coordination: ESA's coordination is required to find a long term solution.
- Technological: Care should be taken to not compromise other aspects. For example, tilted view and large swaths result in harder correction for adjacency in the swath

part in the direction of the tilt. There should be a balance on the missions requirements. A Water Quality mission could be an option.

3.2.5 Virtual constellations to aid data integration and harmonisation (10 responses):

The necessary steps discussed by the attendees for this PA to be carried out can be summarized as follows:

- Coordination: ESA was the Agency cited for coordinating this activity. International cooperation needed, including users' groups. This also can be left to the downstream sector.
- Technological: Acknowledge the projected duration of the missions to be used. Fund studies on harmonizing data and cross-validation. Uncertainties are crucial.

3.3 PA03: Develop a comprehensive suite of water products

Priority Actions

PA03. Develop a comprehensive suite of water products

- 3.1 Products supporting monitoring and management under EU directives
- 3.2 An extended set of water quality products for ecosystem management
- 3.3 Products to support monitoring progress towards the SDGs
- 3.4 Products for all Essential Climate Variables
- 3.5 Atmospherically corrected 'analysis-ready data' products

Figure 12. Priority actions cluster PA03.

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3.3.1 Products supporting monitoring and management under EU Directives

(16 responses):

It was discussed the importance of having a timeline or a typology of applications. This can be inferred from the time of the bottlenecks overcome. There needs to be restated the potential use of EO within EU directives making it more explicit. The necessary steps discussed by the attendees for this PA to be carried out can be summarized as follows:

- Coordination: Water diplomacy. Lobbying. Align the policy cycles with products definition. Agreement at MS level.
- Outreach and Capacity Building: Awareness of what is (and what is not) possible with RS. Show the added value of RS products.
- Technological: Develop demonstration products at European or global scale for supporting the ideas and trade-off analysis. Harmonization of products. Review products every 10 years. Research to find EO - monitoring intersections with new indexes or variables. Guidelines on data processing. Co-develop products by involving scientist (product development), stakeholders (express needs) and operational agencies (operationalization).

3.3.2 An extended set of water quality products for ecosystem management

(16 responses):

The Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) were highlighted inside of this priority. The necessary steps discussed by the attendees for this PA to be carried out can be summarized as follows:

- Coordination: Coordinate with national stakeholders. Perform a holistic approach integrating in situ data, modelling and citizen science with RS. Coordinate with Biodiversity needs. Integrate catchment land use in water management.

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- Technical: Create a list with needed parameters, including EBVs for implementation at EU level. Highlight long term trends analysis with RS to understand ecosystems change. Separate local/regional/pan European needs. Each product listed should have a fitness for purpose.
- Outreach and Capacity Building: Create tools to use the data for management.

3.3.3 Products to support monitoring progress towards the SDGs (12 responses):

It was discussed the idea of creating a Copernicus Hub on SDGs. To the question of why the reporting on SDGs is unequal between countries and how Copernicus can aid, the main discussion was related to the potential of EO to fill gaps, and the acknowledgement that some countries are already overwhelmed with other official reportings. The necessary steps discussed by the attendees for this PA to be carried out can be summarized as follows:

- Coordination: Strengthen the link between Copernicus Services and the UN, specially with WWQA, CEOS and GEO Aquawatch. Showcase real demonstration cases of reporting SDGs with RS (eg. SDG 633)
- Technological: Expansion of Copernicus products to global scale. More in situ data out of EU is needed.

3.3.4 Products for all Essential Climate Variables (11 responses):

In this case, the question of how meaningful short term satellite data could be for climate studies was also discussed. The difference between ECVs and EWWs should be considered to have them under different Services. The necessary steps included by the attendees for this PA to be carried out can be summarized as follows:

- Coordination: Perform a gap analysis and define priorities. Bridge the gap from ESA CCI ECVs to Copernicus operational production.

- Technological: Explore what is already done, or in progress at ESA and C3S level. Exploiting cross ECV questions for inland and coastal areas might be the right focus for future work.

3.3.5 Atmospherically corrected 'analysis-ready data' products (11 responses):

It was highlighted the need to fill the gap in inland water bodies, mainly those small or narrow. The necessary steps discussed by the attendees for this PA to be carried out can be summarized as follows:

- Coordination: Intercomparison exercises and harmonisation.
- Technological: ESA will produce aquatic reflectance as part of the ground segment L2A product, from 2025 onwards, using the AC currently used by marine and land services. A open source stand alone processor included. Supersites: autocalibration and improved AC.

3.4 PA04: Build trust and capacity among users resulting in a water-smart society

Priority Actions

PA04: Build trust and capacity among users resulting in a water-smart society

- 4.1 Increase “satellite literacy” in relevant agencies
- 4.2 Foster synergy between in situ and satellite EO activities with Member States and national agencies
- 4.3 Co-develop products with professionals in the water industry and other end-user sectors (insurance, water utilities, energy etc)
- 4.4 Offer training to national response teams, national statistics departments
- 4.5 Develop projects on Digital Twins, Decision Support Systems, GIS-based knowledge management systems for decision making.

Figure 13. Priority actions cluster PA04.

3.4.1 Increase “satellite literacy” in relevant agencies (11 responses):

The EU Blue Deal was commented in the session as a part of the EU Agenda that can fit into the needs of this priority Action. The necessary steps discussed by the attendees for this PA to be carried out can be summarized as follows:

- Coordination: Open positions for RS experts in relevant agencies.
- Capacity building: understand the agencies needs and build capacity with EO products that can help those needs. Organize trainings. Show demonstration cases.

3.4.2 Foster synergy between in situ and satellite EO activities with Member States and national agencies (13 responses):

It was discussed the lack of overlapping between agencies and activities to be performed. The necessary steps discussed by the attendees for this PA to be carried out can be summarized as follows:

- Coordination: coordinate and technically support national/regional agencies to foster water-body wise cal/val activities and share the results. Earth system models could be the element strengthening synergies. Coordination supported from bottom-up (scientific domain) and top down (UNEP, WWQA...)
- Technical: Development of standardized joint sampling and analyses protocols. Shorten the time until in-situ data are made publicly available.

3.4.3 Co-develop products with professionals in the water industry and other end-user sectors (insurance, water utilities, energy etc) (15 responses):

The discussion raised the question whether water utility and agencies or insurance are business driven and they should be approached differently. The necessary steps discussed by the attendees for this PA to be carried out can be summarized as follows:

- Coordination: coordinate and make use of existing fora for industry / other end users. Find the most engaged and interested companies. Leave this part to the downstream sector.
- Funding: Provide funding for spin-offs and start-ups. Promote funded projects with a commercial exploitation outlook.

3.4.4 Offer training to national response teams, national statistics departments (11 responses):

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The main impediment discussed referred to the local and regional governments not having enough specialized staff to process data, understand uncertainty and implement statistic analyses on the data. The necessary steps discussed by the attendees for this PA to be carried out can be summarized as follows:

- Coordination: Show the added value to raise the need. Establish high level experts at national level. Put in place the needed expert staff.
- Outreach: ESA and Copernicus offer webinars on a continuous and regular basis

3.4.5 Develop projects on Digital Twins, Decision Support Systems, GIS-based knowledge management systems for decision making (12 responses):

Potential overlaps with Digital Twin Earth were discussed. The necessary steps discussed by the attendees for this PA to be carried out can be summarized as follows:

- Coordination: Clarify the respective roles of Destination Earth and Copernicus Services. Act only on clearly identified gaps. Focus on integration into work practice of users.
- Funding: Include key text in Horizon calls. Offer support in form of infrastructure, technical capacity building.

4 Scenarios Session

During this session, the different scenarios for Copernicus Services for water, envisaged by the Water-ForCE team, were explained to the attendees.

- Business as usual (BUA)
- Copernicus Water Thematic Hub (Copernicus TH)
- Advanced Thematic Hub (Advanced TH)
- Water as a dedicated Service.

The following exercise was focused in analysing first, the likelihood of these scenarios towards achieving the “expected impacts” of the call to which Water-ForCE was answering. On a following exercise, the scenarios were further tested against the bottlenecks identified by Water-ForCE.

4.1 How Water-ForCE scenarios will help to achieve the expected impacts:

The two following questions were asked to the attendees:

- How likely is each scenario to deliver the desired impact?
- What is the minimum service level required to achieve the impact?

The attendees were asked to consider the next budget cycle (2028-2035) as the key implementation period whilst allowing for any required R&D, coordination and capacity building to start sooner, if needed.

The deployment of key features mentioned may be part of either core or downstream services, depending on user and industry needs and could exist fully within Copernicus or through international and inter-agency collaboration.

4.1.1 The Service(s) allow us to understand and manage the water cycle as a whole.

The attendees showed a slight preference for the Advanced Thematic Hub Scenario, followed by the Water Service scenario. This last was not rated as high as the Advanced Hub mostly due to the possibility of slowing down the process.

The Service(s) allow us to understand and manage the water cycle as a whole

Figure 14. Response to impact 1.

4.1.2 Monitoring extends across all inland waters.

This impact was considered to be achieved similarly through all the Scenarios, with a preference for the Water Service. BAU was discussed to be more expensive as it fragments services.

Monitoring extends across all inland waters

Figure 15. Response to impact 2.

4.1.3 Service elements have minimal duplication of effort

The continuation with the current configuration of the Services (BAU) was considered not to fulfil the requirements to solve the impact, being more adequate the last 2 scenarios (Advanced Hub and Water Service). If any of these last options are chosen, care should be taken of not losing trust from the current products, while placed under another Service.

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Service elements have minimal duplication of effort

Figure 16. Response to impact 3.

4.1.4 Higher-level biogeochemical products are provided for water quality and food web modelling and analysis

This impact was considered to be easily achieved through the two most advanced Scenarios (Advanced Thematic Hub and Water Service), being the last one considered “very likely” in most cases.

Higher-level biogeochemical products are provided for water quality and food web modelling and analysis

Figure 18. Response to impact 4.

4.1.5 Mixed EO/modelling approaches are deployed, with hindcast and forecast features:

Again the most likely Scenarios that could help achieving this expected impact were considered the two most advanced (Advanced TH and Water Service). It was considered in the discussions that this is an impact that has to happen regardless of what scenario would be put in place. Modelling should be integrated fully even in a BAU scenario. We are moving towards Digital Twins, which implies the necessary use of modelling.

Mixed EO/modelling approaches are deployed, with hindcast and forecast features

Figure 19. Response to impact 5.

4.1.6 Inland and coastal products are mutually consistent or fully integrated across the water continuum:

The integration of products throughout the Water Quality and Quantity continuum was raised as a key point that the current silos structure can not solve. To maintain the consistency through the water cycle and the water continuum, all the relevant products would work better under the same umbrella, whether it is a Hub or a Service.

Inland and coastal products are mutually consistent or fully integrated across the water continuum

Figure 20. Response to impact 6.

4.1.7 Change detection approaches are deployed for water availability quality, storage, fluxes, temperature, lake and river ice and coastal areas

Water as a dedicated Service was the one with higher scores in this case. The discussions did not clearly identify the crucial step to be taken in this scenarios to respond to this expected impact.

Change detection approaches are deployed for wat. availability, wat. quality, wat. storage, wat. fluxes, temperature, lake and river ice and cst areas

Figure 21. Response to impact 8.

4.1.8 Product uncertainties are characterised based on adequate in situ data collection and crowd-sourcing where relevant

The higher likelihood of this impact to be achieved as a result of a new Scenario was considered to happen with a Water Service.

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Product uncertainties are characterised based on adequate in situ data collection and crowd-sourcing where relevant

Figure 22. Response to impact 9.

4.1.9 Non-EO communities in the inland water domain are appropriately engaged to ensure wide uptake of products and services

Again, The higher likelihood of this impact to be achieved, as a result of a new Scenario, was considered to happen with a Water Service. This is the first impact which has a difference because Services get user uptake funds, so considering a new Service will actually help to achieve this goal.

Non-EO communities in the inland water domain are appropriately engaged to ensure wide uptake of products and services

Figure 23. Response to impact 10.

4.2 How Water-ForCE scenarios will help to overcome the identified bottlenecks?

Two questions were asked to the attendees regarding each identified bottleneck:

- How likely is each scenario to overcome each bottleneck?
- What is the minimum service level required to overcome each bottleneck?

4.2.1 A dedicated in-situ component is established to support water-related services

In this case the Water Service was clearly identified as the best scenario to overcome this bottleneck, while the discussions in the audience were around the organization of the in situ data collection to be as useful as possible for the Copernicus Services.

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A dedicated in-situ component is established to support water-related services

Figure 24. Response to bottleneck 1.

4.2.2 Copernicus water products are trusted by end-users:

This bottleneck was considered to be increasingly possible to be overcome as the scenarios get more advanced.

Copernicus water products are trusted by end-users

Figure 25. Response to bottleneck 2.

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4.2.3 EO and EU directives are compatible

In this case, the projected scenarios were not considered to clearly overcome the bottleneck. The discussions in the group were around the demand process for EO products. It was discussed the fact chain starting from the EU Directives definitions and reporting needs.

EO and EU directives are compatible

Figure 26. Response to bottleneck 3.

4.2.4 Copernicus products and Services for water can be integrated seamlessly across the water continuum

Again, as the Scenarios are more advanced, the attendees showed more confidence in the bottleneck to be overcome. Copernicus products for water are considered to be more easily integrated and coherent if they are under the same umbrella, whether this is an Advanced Hub or a dedicated Service.

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Copernicus products and Services for water can be integrated seamlessly across the water continuum

Figure 27. Response to bottleneck 4.

4.2.5 Space-based assets are suitably optimised for inland waters

The attendees considered that this bottleneck is most likely to be overcome with a dedicated Water Service. In order to push space based assets ESA would need to take into account inland and coastal water component in a concrete way (explicitly as part of the enhancement).

Space-based assets are suitably optimised for inland waters

Figure 28. Response to bottleneck 5.

4.2.6 Funding mechanisms support expansion of the inland water services product portfolio (including data collection, R&D)

Again the Water Service was chosen as the most feasible Scenario to overcome this bottleneck. It was discussed that this could be more a matter of distribution of the funds. Focus is needed towards bringing existing algorithms and methods to an EU or global scale intercomparison or validation to make operational products.

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Funding mechanisms support expansion of the inland water services product portfolio (including data collection, R&D)

Figure 29. Response to bottleneck 6.

4.2.7 All relevant user communities are appropriately engaged and aware of the service portfolio.

Again, as the Scenarios are more advanced, the attendees showed more confidence in this bottleneck to be overcome, considering it more likely if a Water Service is established.

All relevant user communities are appropriately engaged and aware of the service portfolio

Figure 30. Response to bottleneck 7.

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4.2.8 Requirements and expertise in the water domain are recognised and understood within the Copernicus Programme.

In this case, the Water Service was clearly considered the better option. The discussion led to the acknowledgement that the existence of a concrete body responsible for inland waters, then they will get a stronger voice, considering that Water Service would enable water recognition within the Copernicus Programme.

Requirements and expertise in the water domain are recognised and understood within the Copernicus Programme

Figure 31. Response to bottleneck 8.

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8.6.3 Report on Executive Board and Advisory Board Meetings

The Advisory Board in Water-ForCE has been following the steps of the development of the Roadmap, since the first outline towards the final document that will be released at the end of the project.

The composition of the Advisory Board changed during the course of the action, but the roles and responsibilities as well as the representativeness from the needed institutions and domains were always maintained.

To protect personal data and opinions of the AB members we will just describe the dates and objectives of the 3 major meetings.

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1 Meetings (26-28/01/2021 & 28/02/2022)

The first meeting of the Advisory Board members with the whole Consortium and hence with the Executive Board was during the Kick-off meeting (**26th-28th January, 2021**); in which the AB Members present gave their view about the project. The objective of this meeting was to present the project plans and the specific role of the consortium members to achieve the planned outcomes.

The objectives of the meeting celebrated on **28/02/2022** (one year later) were to summarize the first year of work of Water-ForCE, present the first outline of the Roadmap and agree on the next actions to be taken.

The AB members had the Technical Periodic Report (Part B) covering the first 12 months of the project, to properly evaluate the work done and the Work Packages presentations with a summary of the work per WP.

The Coordinator gave an overview of the project and presented the current outline of the Roadmap document, to be discussed with the AB members.

The outcomes were further implemented in the development of the next version of the Roadmap.

The meeting was duly minuted.

2 Meeting 2 (26/05/2022)

The second Executive Board and Advisory Board Meeting was celebrated **on 26/05/2022 in Bonn during the Livin Planet Symposium 2022**. They were present on site Executive Board Members or representers from WP2, 3, 4,5,6 and 8 and the Coordinator. WP1 representer attended remotely. From the Advisory Board Arnold Dekker and Giuseppe Ottaviannelli were present on site and Bastiaan Ibelings attended remotely. The Agenda Items were:

- Coordinator presentation
- Roadmap Draft Presentation
- Questions to the AB Members
- Discussion

As supporting documentation, the AB members received the Roadmap Draft in advance and a set of specific questions related to their institution or field of expertise., that were discussed during the meeting.

3 Meeting 3 (30/05/2023 & 21/06/2023)

The 3rd meeting with the AB members had to be done in 2 different meetings because of the impossibility of all the AB members to be present at the same time.

In both meetings, the AB members received the current version of the Roadmap 2 weeks in advance. That version was in an advanced state, so the questions and discussions were more specific and focused in achieving a proper format and content for an actionable Roadmap.

The first meeting was organized 30th May 2023, as a hybrid event with the on-site part in Amsterdam, for this to be a central point in Europe, easier to reach. To that meeting, the AB members attending were Arnold Dekker (SatDeck), Bastiaan Ibelings (GLEON) and Henrik S. Andersen (EEA).

The second meeting took place as an on-line event and the AB members attending were Giuseppe Ottavianelli (ESA) and Luca de Felice (JRC).

All meetings were duly minuted and minutes sent for review.

